

Signs of the Creative Influence of Representatives of the Lake School in P. Shelley's Poetry

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Abstract:

It is described that the emergence of English romantic poetry in world literature is related to the traditions of Eastern literature in terms of folklore, ancient literature, artistic form and content. In this article, the harmony of the poetry of P.B.Shelley.

Keywords: English romanticism, Eastern traditions, devil, devil, hell, poem, symbol, figurative meaning, goodness and evil, oriental images, romantic landscape, black vices, rhythmic structure.

Percy Bysshe Shelley is one of the authors who left a big mark on the English romantic literature despite his youth. Although he lived for only thirty years, he managed to create valuable works like Hamid Olimjan, Usman Nasir, poets of Uzbek literature. Sonnets and ballads occupy the main place in contemporaries such as Wordsworth and Blake, while epics and dramas play an important role in Shelley's work. His epics are written in the form of odes, i.e. like odes, and are titled: "Ode to the Wind Blowing in the Maghreb", "Ode to the Sky", etc. Another characteristic of him, which was different from the romantic artists who left a mark in the literature of the time, was the idea of freedom in his work and the spirit of rebellion against any restrictions and shackles. Through the "Queen Mab" saga, he expressed the life of the oppressors, reactionaries, people who rebelled against religion and are suffering in the conditions of hard labor and slavery all over the world. This is due to his selfish mentality. Shelley also participated in the freedom wars fought by the Irish people in Dublin. "The invincibility of the forces of life, love and freedom is expressed in Shelley's "Ode to the Wind Blowing from the Maghreb", and the celebration of love over oppression and death in "Islamic Rebellion" (1818) and "Epipsidixion" (1821).

While living in Italy, Shelley turned to the novel genre and created the figurative "lyrical drama" "Prometheus Unchained" (1819) based on the ancient Greek myth and Aeschylus' drama "Prometheus in Chains", and the tragedy "Cenchi" (1819) based on the plot of a medieval Italian chronicle. ". References to Greek mythology or ancient literature are found in many of his plays.

The choice of the image of Prometheus also indicates the idea of will in the poet's works. In "Prometheus Freed", "Shelley connects his dream of freedom with the image of the great, great Prometheus, who has been the friend and savior of mankind since ancient times."

This work, written in the spirit of Aeschylus' tragedy "Golden-Banded Prometheus", depicts a rebellion against Jupiter. Prometheus foresaw the fate of Jupiter. Mythical sources mention the ability of Prometheus to foresee the fate of the gods. Fantastic-mythological plots are included in many of the poet's works. Shelley took the literature of this period as the main source for his work because the works of Sophocles, Aeschylus, Homer embodied the images of people's hopes and dreams. He also met the great English poet Byron. There is a similarity in the fate of these creators: both of them experienced the fate of persecution. In this sense, they can be called "rebellious romanticists" among representatives of English romantic literature. He was forced to go to Italy in 1818 and spent the last four years of his life there, creating several works that are the peak of his creativity. "Islamic Rebellion", "Prometheus Unleashed", "Chenji" are among them. The artistic excellence and perfection of Shelley's works is due to the fact that he is a mature literary critic. His tract called "Poetry of Defense" is a work dedicated to the theory of literature created in a critical spirit. This work confirms that Shelley was a creative philosopher. For Shelley, who had a deep knowledge of ancient Greek literature, the combination of philosophical ideas was not random or a collection of sciences that took time to learn.

In English romanticism, Shelley is the writer who wrote about the most happiness or the most despair. He started writing poetry while studying at Eton. Some of his poems were published in the magazine "Original poetry" at that time.

Shelley was not indifferent to the artists of his time, Wordsworth and Coleridge. He understood the pantheistic ideas of Wordsworth and the mystical ideas of Coleridge. Shelley created a rebellious poetry that stood out from them. He did not follow the path of gradual explanation through the medium of images. Perhaps he directed each of his words directly to the human heart, and there he called for the freedom of the soul that has been suffering for ages.

Dedicated to the idea that "love is everywhere celebrated as the only law that should govern the moral world," The Revolt of Islam provides a poetic forum for Shelley to denounce tyranny, religious fraud, war, oppressors, and their consequences. The poet reflects on "civil war", famine, plague, superstition and the complete disappearance of domestic affection and hope, enlightenment, love, "moral dignity and freedom". This work was created as a result of revision of "Laon and Cynthia". He has visions of an ideal future. The poet considers himself the "immortal voice of truth" and says in the epic: "I did not try to recommend methodical and systematic arguments instead of the ideas that currently govern mankind. I would only stir up the emotions to make the reader see the beauty of true virtue and prompt the inquiries that lead to my moral and political convictions."

The experiences reflected in Shelley's epic "Ode to Heaven" give people strength. The poet wrote this work in 1820, and before that he experienced many adventures. In him was embodied the strongest degree of any emotion. Shelley called heaven "home of eternity". The artist's life, full of hardships and difficulties, prompts him to stay with happy dreams that have passed for a while. This work, created in the spirit of the evening stroll, can be understood in the spirit of searching for something ideal and elusive. The main points expressed by the three spirits form the content of the poem. There is also an allusion to God here, and the symbol of the sun's flame at night indicated that there is a light like man in the darkness of the psyche:

Землю к жизни ты воззвал,
Свет великой жизни дал
Сонму звезд в бездонных безднах,
И косматые планеты

Носятся в пучинах звездных,
Ты зажег миры, планеты,
Пламень солнц в ночной стихии,
Блещут луны ледяные

И светила огневые Images such as stars, planets, sky, and sun described in the poem carry vital meaning. In the poet's interpretation, they rule human life, the whole being consists of stars, sun and sky.

And pine for what is not –

Our sincerest laughter

With some pain is fraught –

Our sweetest songs are those that tell of saddest thought.

The above lines reflect the desire to alleviate the pains of humanity, which lives without understanding itself. When the poet says, "The sweetest songs sing the saddest thoughts," he means exactly these pains. Various complex situations in the human heart are expressed.

In Shelley's poetry, the poetic expression of the most beautiful intimate feelings of a person stands out as an important feature of the image style. As difficult as it is to express these feelings at times, Shelley manages to do so.

The optimistic spirit in the poet's works shows that he can find a solution to every problem. But it should be noted that his critical works, rich in social ideas approaching realism, reflected disappointments and depression.

"Prometheus Freed" is a lyrical drama of the poet, consisting of four acts. It is known that Prometheus was sentenced to eternal punishment at the hands of Zeus because of the good he did to mankind. Only his eventual abdication freed Prometheus. Shelley compares his ideal hero Prometheus to Satan in Milton's Paradise Lost. But it did not depend on the character of the characters, it meant the degree of grandeur, power and basic heroism in them. While imagining Prometheus as the savior, the reader does not forget that Zeus (Jupiter) is a powerful being. But Shelley's Jupiter, unlike Aeschylus', is unable to overcome Prometheus. And his Prometheus is a revolutionary. The events of the play refer to the French Revolution. The epilogue, spoken by the Demogorgon, reveals Shelley's revolutionary speech:

To suffer woes which Hope thinks infinite;

To forgive wrongs darker than death or night;

To defy Power, which seems omnipotent;

To love, and bear; to hope till Hope creates

From its own wreck the thing it contemplates;

Neither to change, nor falter, nor repent;

This, like thy glory, Titan, is to be

Good, great and joyous, beautiful and free;

This is alone Life, Joy, Empire, and Victory.

(Experience sorrows that hope is boundless;

Forgiveness of sins darker than death and night;

Opposing a Power that seems mighty;
 To love and endure;
 To hope until hope creates from its destruction what it thinks;
 No change, no admiration, no repentance;
 This, like your majesty, Titan,
 is to be good, great and joyful, beautiful and free;
 This alone is life, joy, empire and victory).

Prometheus is referred to in this through the Titan mentioned. Living hoping for a change in the society, system, and leadership forces the common people to forgive their sins, darker than night and darker than death. Even in Shelley's poems, where natural scenes are harmoniously described, the lyrical hero hopes to win some kind of endless struggle. Indeed, this is an important characteristic of romanticism. Therefore, his poem called "Song" also has a motive of desperate hope. In the fields covered with cold snow, among the thickets of spruce and birch, feeding on dead branches without a single leaf, a lonely bird cries:

Percy Bysshe Shelley's work follows the ideas of Byron. The poet's sonnet dedicated to Byron is a proof of this. His ability to describe epic reality in lyrics is unique. Undoubtedly, his poems and lyrical tragedies played an important role in the literature of this period. In his treatise "A Defense of Poetry", he says: "Poetry must be absorbed into the body of the whole human society before it disappears." This applies not only to poetry, but also to its creator. In fact, Shelley's poetry was able to penetrate the body of people all over the world.

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